

Effect of Migration on the Provision of Social Amenities in Urban Centres in Enugu State

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effect of migration on the provision of social amenities in urban centers in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare; evaluation of the effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply and the effect of movement rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study consisted of three hundred and fifty one (351) owners and staff. The whole population was used due to small number. Three hundred and forty six (346) persons returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 99 percent response rate. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool. The findings indicated i. Transit to a new environment had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 346), 8.279 < 10.293, P. < .05$; Acclimation to a new location had significant positive effect on the provision of electricity supply $Z(95, n = 346), 9.919 < 10.833, P. < .05$ and Movement from rural-urban had significance positive effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state, $Z(95, n = 346), 9.650 < 11.102, P. < .05$. The study concluded that transit to a new environment, Acclimation to a new location and Movement from rural-urban had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare, electricity supply and pipe borne in Urban Centres in Enugu State. The recommended among others that there is need for rural development to reduce why people migrate in search of income differences in the urban centres.

Keywords Effect of Migration; Social Amenities; Urban Centers; Provision of Healthcare; Provision of Electricity Supply

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Introduction

All living organisms require a suitable environment in which to survive and thrive. Migration, as a whole, captures a dynamic, constantly changing reality. The change in the social status from non-migrant to migrant causes change in norms and values, attitudes and behavior, motivation and expectation, material and social status, social priority and change in the circle of interaction. All these changes have a negative effect on fertility level and family size. Since its inception, the migration phenomenon is manifesting on a global level, with advantages and disadvantages and represents an indisputable element of our age, which influences the social and economic life of the states. Faced with this reality, the governments of the world have to seek the most effective ways of interstate cooperation regarding migration (Tataru, 2019). Migration is a feature of social and economic life across many countries, but the profile of migrant populations varies considerably. Understanding these impacts is important if our societies are to usefully debate the role of migration. Such debates, in turn, are essential to designing policies in areas like education and employment that maximise the benefits of migration, especially by improving migrants' employment situation (OECD, 2014).

An important social consequence of migration is its effect on the processes of acculturation and adjustment and integration of migrants in the receiving areas. Migration is a feature of social and economic life across many countries, but the profile of migrant populations varies considerably. The economic impact of migration has been intensively studied but is still often driven by ill-informed perceptions, which, in turn, can lead to public antagonism towards migration. These negative views risk jeopardizing efforts to adapt migration policies to the new economic and demographic challenges facing many countries (OECD, (2014). Voluntary migration is based on the initiative and the free will of the person and is influenced by a combination of factors: economic, political and social: either in the migrants' country of origin (determinant factors or "push factors") or in the country of destination. Migration is becoming a very important subject for the life of cities. Many opportunities and attraction of big cities pull large numbers of people to big cities. Migration can have positive as well as negative effects on the life of the migrants. Increased migration levels typically result in increased economic growth indicators, making amenity migration an attractive rural development strategy. Zhonglei, Hua, and Jinshe, (2019) asserts that regarding amenities, migrants prefer to move into cities with warm winters, less-humid summers, clean urban environments and friendly and open social climates. Social services, including facilities for education, recreation and commuting, also play an important role in attracting migrants.

Social amenities can be anything that boosts social relationships or extends a social courtesy to others. The most daunting challenge faced by citizens and other individuals is the lack of social amenities generally as well as their inadequate and poor provision where they exist. Also, the wide disparity in social amenities provision between villages or rural areas and towns is worrisome. This is because the cities attract more of these facilities than the rural areas. Social amenities critical to human existence and social growth as well as economic uplift include good roads, railways, waterways, housing, potable and safe water, power, security, and job creation (Editor, 2021). The broader processes of social change shape migration, through its social, economic, cultural, demographic and political impacts; to some extent migration also affects these processes in its own right. Migration aspirations depend on people's more general life aspirations and their perceptions of the extent to which these aspirations can be fulfilled 'here' and 'there'. Both these aspirations and perceptions about geographical opportunities are highly subjective and likely to change under the influence of social and cultural change.

Statement of the problem

The free movement of persons is part of a myriad of problems, combined with terrorism and territorial security, with the protection of fundamental human rights, as well as with the permanent need for improvement and adjustment of government in order to streamline population control in sovereign states. Migration is the movement of people from their original habitat to a destination outside the borders of their origin, purposely to settle and can be voluntary or forced. The consequences of migration are usually not predetermined, due to various stages of uncertainty that may arise, to deter the motive of the migrant to relocate.

The economic impact of migration has been intensively studied but is still often driven by ill-informed perceptions, which, in turn, can lead to public antagonism towards migration. These negative views risk jeopardizing efforts to adapt migration policies to the new economic and demographic challenges facing many countries. Migrants are often faced with challenges of being accepted by host communities, hence the difficulties in communal integration, harmonious living, commerce, cultural practices, religious beliefs, language barriers, agricultural practices, economic activities, social integration and pastoralism. Also, these migrants also find it difficult to successfully transit to a new environment and be acclimatized with their new location.

Migration is a feature of social and economic life across many countries, but the profile of migrant populations varies considerably. Migrants contribute significantly to economic integration, whereby the migrants are the agents of economic diversity through cross-border trade activities. However, the social and economic benefits accrued are at par with emerging security threats along border communities, such as human trafficking, smuggling of contraband, proliferation of small arms and light weapons and narcotic trafficking. When there are high rate of migrants in a given geographical location, it becomes difficult for social amenities such as healthcare and electricity to be enough. It is against this backdrop that the researcher sought to evaluate the effect of migration on the provision of social amenities in urban centers in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to evaluate the effect of migration on the provision of social amenities in urban centers in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban centers in Enugu State
- ii. Evaluation of the effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in urban centers in Enugu State
- iii. Ascertain the effect of movement rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study

- i. What is the effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban centers in Enugu State
- ii. What is the effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in urban centers in Enugu State
- iii. What is the effect of movement rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Transit to a new environment has effect on the provision of healthcare in urban centers in Enugu State
- ii. Acclimation to a new location has effect on the provision of electricity supply in urban centers in Enugu State
- iii. Movement from rural-urban has effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state

Significance of the Study

Migration will help in the improving the quality of life of people, improve social life of people as they learn about new culture, customs, and languages which helps to improve brotherhood among people. Migration of skilled workers leads to a greater economic growth of the region.

Scope of the Study

The study based on the effect of migration on the provision of social amenities in urban centers in Enugu state. The key variables used in the study were transit to a new environment, acclimation to a new location and Movement from rural-urban as the independent variable while provision of healthcare, provision of electricity and provision of pipe borne water were the dependent variables. The geographical scope of the study was Enugu State.

Review of related literature

Conceptual review

Migration

Migration is the movement of living things from one abode to another. This involves movement of people from one country, residence and locality to another. Migration is, first and foremost, a normal human activity. Toney and Bailey, (2014) defined migration within demography, as a movement that results in a long-term or permanent change in usual place of residence. In operational terms, migration is typically defined as a move that crosses a specified political boundary, such as a county, or moves into a different labor market for the purpose of establishing a new place of residence. Migration within a country is referred to as internal migration, and migration that crosses a national boundary is called immigration or emigration. Human beings have always moved from 'one country, locality, (and) place of residence to settle in another'. Tataru, (2019) asserts that migration is a phenomenon of great complexity. The reasons people migrate are varied and constantly changing. Moreover, the individuals who migrate are not easy to classify due to the fact that they come under different circumstances, from different environments and with different individual characteristics. Accordingly, understanding the causes and consequences of migration, as well as acquiring theoretical and practical skills are essential for both tackling the challenges that arise and developing effective policies to protect migrants. People move in search of work or economic opportunities, to join family, or to study. Others move to escape conflict, persecution, terrorism, or human rights violations. Still others move in response to the adverse effects of climate change, natural disasters, or other environmental factors.

Components of Migration used in the Study

Transit to a new environment

Transition to a new environment occurs as a result of natural and human processes. A new environment might mean a new job, a new school, a new rental share, or moving in with your partner. One way to make the transition easier is to focus on the positive elements of the new environment. Taking the time to explore the local culture, cuisine, and landscape can help to create a sense of familiarity and connection. Building relationships with locals and other newcomers can also help to create a sense of community (Neecey, 2015). Environmental systems and human activities contribute to environmental changes through the transformation and transportation of large quantities of energy and materials. Evolutionary adaptation, or simply adaptation, is the adjustment of organisms to their environment in order to improve their chances at survival in that environment. One of the challenges of transiting to a new environment is how to navigate the different changes and the obstacles that may stand in the way as individuals gradually begin to adapt to new lives in an unfamiliar environment.

Acclimation to a New Location

Acclimation involves physiological, anatomical, or morphological adjustments within a single organism that improve performance or survival in response to environmental change. The term "Acclimatization" refers to a process where an organism adjusts to changes in its environment with respect to temperature, altitude, humidity, pH, light, salinity, pressure and presence of certain chemicals. *It is also defined as a process where an organism adjusts its behaviour or physiology in response to changes in its environment. The changes in the physiology and behaviour of a single organism happen in a short period of time within its lifetime* (Byju, 2023). Acclimatization is a short-term rapid temporary adjustment of an organism to a changing environment. Acclimatization is a quick, temporary change that can be reversed once the previous conditions are met and often occurs during an organism's lifetime (Vedantu, 2023).

Movement from Rural-Urban

Rural to urban migration means that people choose to move from a less populated area to more densely populated areas which often present more work opportunities, better pay, or a better quality of life. People living in rural areas are more likely to migrate than those living in urban cities (Selod and Shilpi, 2021). Cities have developed into centers of industry, commerce, education, and entertainment. The allure of city living and the many opportunities that may come with it have long driven people to uproot and settle in the city. Rural-to-urban migration is when people move, either temporarily or permanently, from a rural area to an urban city. Rural-to-urban migration occurs at both the national and international level, but internal or national migration takes place at a higher rate. This type of migration is voluntary, meaning that migrants willingly choose to relocate. However, rural-to-urban migration can also be forced in some cases, such as when rural refugees flee to urban areas. Developing countries characteristically have higher rates of rural-to-urban migration compared to countries with more developed (Studysmarter, 2023).

Social Amenities

Social amenities are structures that people, individuals, and communities need to take care of basic needs of life. Some of them include hospitals, banks, parks, and libraries. Developing social amenities is good both for individuals and communities in the long run. Social amenities in a place are one of the catalysts for economic growth. They can attract businesses to a place, which in turn leads to increased economic activity and job creation (Populace, 2023). Social amenities involves desirable or useful facility or service that offers individuals a pleasurable social experience, an added value quality service, freely available, within the wider community and/or family environment. Social amenities provide opportunities for recreation and foster a sense of oneness and make the community more attractive. Access to social Amenities inspires life and well being. This in turn breeds a sense of self-reliance, national pride and also aids the realization of full potentials and opportunities by the individual thereby reducing inequalities among the citizenry. social amenities such as hospitals, schools, recreational centers and green areas tends to foster healthy living and has a significant on individual life style which will go a long way to unify both the government and private partnership in providing liable environment and business atmosphere (Eduproject, 2017).

Component of Social Amenities used in the Study

Provision of Healthcare

Provision of healthcare means providing, or failing to provide, healthcare or advice to a patient in a professional capacity by a practice entity or any practice staff. Health care provision refers to the way inputs such as money, staff, equipment and drugs are combined to deliver health interventions. Health care includes all services dealing with the diagnosis and treatments of disease, or the promotion, maintenance and restoration of health including personal and non-personal health services (WHO, 2016). While provision refers to the way inputs such as money, staff, equipment and drugs are combined to allow the delivery of health interventions (WHO, 2016). Health care is conventionally regarded as an important determinant in promoting the general physical and mental health and well-being of people around the world. Limitations to health care services affect negatively the use of medical services, the efficacy of treatments, and overall outcome. It is the prevention, treatment, and management of illness and the preservation of mental and physical well-being through the services offered by the medical, nursing, and allied health professions. According to the World Health Organisation a health system consists of all organisations, people and actions whose primary intent is to promote, restore or maintain health. This includes efforts to influence determinants of health as well as more direct activities that improve health. A health system is, therefore, more than the pyramid of publicly owned facilities that deliver personal health services but include the institutions, people and resources involved in delivering health care to individuals (Physiopedia, 2023). Generally, the goal of health care provision is to improve health outcomes in the population and to respond to people's expectations, while reducing inequalities in both health and responsiveness

Provision of Electricity Supply

Electricity provision requires the combination of successive services into a bundle to be supplied to final consumers: power generation itself, electricity transmission, voltage and frequency control, and the sequence of tasks designated to ensure the necessary reliability. Electricity provision is a rival good because individual consumption has an impact on the quantity available to the residual demand; it can also be considered non-excludable due to the difficulty in excluding those that do not pay for the service provided (Rubino, 2017). Electric power distribution is the final stage in the delivery of electricity. Electricity is carried from the transmission system to individual consumers.

Provision of Pipe Borne Water

Following the adoption of the National Water Supply and Sanitation Policy in January 2000, the Nigerian Government considered the provision of water supply services to be the domain of the Federal, State and Local Governments. However, the public sector was not successful in meeting more than a small portion of the demand for water by residential and commercial users. Services were critically in short supply. For example, out of the 85 million people (Federal Republic of Nigeria,) living in urban and semi urban areas, less than half have reasonable access to reliable water supply. Many urban households, often the poorest, end up purchasing water from private vendors at a higher price than the public supply. A few rural communities were provided with hand-operated boreholes and wells which yield little or no water during the dry seasons due to incessant breakdown and fall in the water table. Water supply services, where they exist, are unreliable and of low quality; and are not sustainable because of difficulties in management, operation and pricing as well as due to failure to recover costs. Many water supply systems show extensive deterioration and poor utilization of existing capacities, due to under-maintenance and lack of funds for operation (Ishaku, Majid Ajayi, & Haruna, 2021).

Theoretical Frameworks

The study made use of Lee's migration model 1996 and Human Relation Theory by Professor Elton Mayo 1932. The study anchored on Lee's migration model.

Lee's Migration Model 1966

Lee's migration model created in 1966 describes the push and pulls factors of migration which are basically reasons for emigration and immigration. A push factor is something that is unfavorable about the area that someone lives in and is a reason for them to leave. Lee's migration model is a model that accounts for push/pull factors and intervening obstacles in order to predict migration patterns. Everett Spurgeon Lee, Professor of Sociology at the University of Georgia is known for his pioneering theory of migration, which is known as the Push and Pull Theory, or also as Lee' Theory. Lee first presented his model at the Annual meeting of Mississippi Valley Historical Association. The theory, which draws on principles of sociology, attempts to formalize a 'theory' of migration which would provide a scheme of the factors that could explain the volume of migration between origin and destination. Lee's theory is both simple and has withstood the test of times. Everett Lee has conceptualized the factors associated with the decision to migrate and the process of migration into the following four categories: (1) Factors associated with the area of origin; (2) Factors associated with the area of destination; (3) Intervening obstacles; and (4) Personal factors. Lee elaborates all these four categories by pointing out that, in each area, there are numerous factors which act to drive away the people from the area, or to hold the people in the area or to attract the people to it. In this respect, there are significant differences between the factors associated with the area of origin and those associated with the area of destination. Migration may take place after both these are properly weighed. Usually, however, a person has a better and more realistic knowledge about the place of origin, while his knowledge about the place of destination is somewhat superficial and inexact. Intervening obstacles also have to be overcome before migration finally takes place. These include distance and transportation. Technological advances, however, have lessened their importance in modern times. Finally, the personal factors are of the utmost importance because, instead of the actual factors associated with the place of origin and/or destination, the individual's perception of these factors is found to influence the actual act of migration.

Human Relation Theory

Human Relation Theory was proposed by Professor Elton Mayo 1932. The theory focuses specifically on the individual's needs and resultant behaviors of individuals and groups. It takes an interpersonal approach to managing human beings. It presents the organization is made up of formal and informal elements. The formal elements of an organization are its structure. The informal aspects of the organization include the interactions between individuals. In this way, the organization is a type of social system. This system should be managed to create individual job satisfaction and the resultant motivation of the individual. The Elton Mayo Human Relations Theory showed that relationships are highly influential for human productivity. Employers and managers need to have a vast array of skills to effectively carry a human relations-focused workplace culture. Notably, much emphasis is placed on how individuals interact within groups and the result group behavior and performance (Gordon, 2022). Human relations are the interactions that take place within a business setting. The human relations concept also revolves around the study of people's issues arising from organizational and interpersonal relations. This encompasses any form of interactions between the clients, suppliers, workers, and management, all of which are geared toward achieving the organization's goals, and objectives. In a business, human resources are knowledgeably managed through a focus on the inorganization events, attitudes, opinions, and the interrelationships of different stakeholders (Bryce, 2022).

Empirical Review of the Study

The effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State

Nnebue, Echendu, and Sidney-nnebue (2014), conducted a study on Urbanization and health - an overview. The rapid increase in the number of people living in urban areas is among the most important global health issues of the 21st century. Also, most developing countries are facing the task of planning and ensuring a sustainable, sane and healthy development of cities. To review the relationship between urbanization and health with emphasis on approach and options for the promotion of healthy behaviours and safety. The main sources of information were online journals, Pub Med/Medline and Google. Additionally, publications from the World Health Organisation and public libraries were consulted for articles on urbanization and its impacts on health. The health of urban populations has changed as cities have evolved as a result of such factors as features of the social environment, the physical environment, and provision of and access to health and social services. The urban context of particular cities may also affect health as well as modify the effect that unexpected stressors have on a city. Reliable urban health statistics are largely unavailable globally. However, available data indicate a range of urban health hazards and associated health risks that cut across different sectors, including health, environment, energy, transportation and urban planning. Governments are grappling with the challenges posed by the speed at which urbanization has outpaced their ability to provide essential infrastructure. There is need for planned urbanization to help avert the negative effects of urban living on health.

Alhaji, and Lawal (2017), conducted a study on Urbanization, Cities, and Health: The Challenges to Nigeria – A Review. The Nigerian society is rapidly becoming urban as a result of a multitude of push and pull factors. This has generated urban health crises among city dwellers notably the urban poor. A systematic search of published literature in English was conducted between 1960 and 2015. Published peer review journals, abstracts, Gray literature (technical reports, government documents, reports, etc.), inaugural lectures, and internet articles were reviewed. Manual search of reference lists of selected articles were checked for further relevant studies. The review showed that the pace of urbanization is unprecedented with cities such as Lagos having annual urban growth rate of 5.8%. Urbanization in Nigeria is mainly demographically driven without commensurate socioeconomic dividends and benefits to the urban environment. This has created urban health crises of inadequate water safe supply, squalor and shanty settlements, sanitation, solid waste management, double burden of diseases and inefficient, congested, and risky transport system. In conclusion, when managed carefully, urbanization could reduce hardship and human suffering; on the other hand, it could also increase poverty and squalor. Some laws need to be amended to change the status of poor urban settlements. Urban health development requires intersectoral approach with political will and urban renewal program to make our urban societies sustainable that promote healthy living.

Egbenta, Smart, and Okwuchi (2021), established a study on Effects of Noise Pollution on Residential Property Value in Enugu Urban, Nigeria. One of the persistent environmental issues today is high noise levels in residential areas especially in the developing countries. There are several unorganized informal sector activities such as recreational, road traffic, household and religious activities, operation of power generating sets, incompatible uses in space among others that are the sources of noise pollution in residential areas. A number of empirical studies have been carried out on the impact of noise on residential property values. However, one finds it very difficult to ascertain whether noise pollution affects residential property value in Enugu Urban. The aim of this study is to ascertain whether noise pollution has significant influence on residential rental values in the study area. The study has discovered that residential properties affected by noise pollution have lower rental value compared to those unaffected by 3.1% of its rental value. The study has provided some insight to guide property buyers or users, investors, property managers, and values as regards property transactions. The study has suggested that property value spatial index of noise pollution in the study area can be built and use as a guide for urban management strategy to achieve sustainable development.

Timothy, Stephen, and Richard (2023) conducted a study on Perceived Health Impacts, Sources of Information and Individual Actions to Address Air Quality in Two Cities in Nigeria. Poor air quality (PAQ) has serious effects on the environment, climate change, and human health. This study investigated the perceived health impacts of PAQ in two cities in Nigeria (Abuja and Enugu), including whether PAQ may have an interaction with COVID-19 infection and intensity. A recent report published in the Lancet has pointed to the complexity of the health care system in Nigeria and a lack of data on disease burden, so the research in this paper took a self-reporting (perceptual) approach to exploring the health impacts of PAQ. The research also sought to explore the main sources of information used by people to inform them about air quality (AQ) and the actions they are likely to take to address PAQ. The results imply that many of the respondents in the two cities perceived their health to be adversely affected by PAQ and that PAQ worsens both the chances of infection and the intensity of COVID-19. Unsurprisingly, older people were found to be more vulnerable to the health impacts of PAQ. Most respondents, especially younger ones, obtained their information on AQ via electronic media (internet, social media) rather than printed media. Respondents considered that the primary action to address PAQ is proper waste management. Paying the government to address PAQ was regarded as the least likely action, although the government was acknowledged as having a key responsibility.

Etalong, and Ezeodili (2023) conducted a study on Effect of planning on Housing Development in Enugu State. The importance of good policy formulation and detailed implementation cannot be overemphasized as it aid proper planning for developmental purposes, it is on this note that effective planning is crucial to housing development. The central objective of this is to examine the effect of planning on housing development in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study make use of descriptive research design while data were sourced using both primary and secondary data with the help of questionnaire which was distributed among 90 staff of Enugu state Economic Planning Commission, Enugu state Ministry of Land and Urban Development and Enugu State Housing Development Corporation. The data obtained were analyzed using table and lines, the result shows that effective planning bring about the following in housing development: Organized and Sustainable Growth, Infrastructure Development, Affordable Housing, Improved Housing Standards, Reduced Informal Settlements, Preservation of Cultural Heritage, Environmental Protection and Traffic Management. The result further identify challenges confronting effective planning on housing development, these include: Lack of Political Will, Inadequate Financial Resources, Land Availability and Acquisition, Bureaucratic Red Tape, Community Opposition and NIMBYism, Infrastructure Limitations, Environmental Concerns, Lack of Expertise and Capacity, Corruption and Mismanagement and Social and Cultural Considerations.

The effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State

Eyankware, Eyankware, Okoeguale, and Eyankware (2015) conducted a study on the Impact of Increase in Urbanization on Major Cities in Nigeria. A Case Study of Enugu State (Enugu Urban), Southeastern Nigeria. The increase in migration into urban cities in Nigeria has posed a challenge to the Nigerian government. This study assessed the causes of rural-urban migration in major cities in Nigeria of which Enugu Urban is a case study. There are several factors responsible for rural-urban migration which influence the migrant's migration status. The study attempts to find answers to research questions by using survey design and sampling techniques to collect data from 210 (153) respondents with the aid of a 10-item structured questionnaire and personal interview. The respondents

comprise of heads of household of migrants' (remove this) in the study area. Data for this study were edited, coded and analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that majority of the migrants migrated to continue their education rather than in search of employment as concluded by a lot of past studies. It also revealed that the impact of out-migration in the area includes: absence of youths to assist parents in their profession, lack of work force to work on farms, and desertion of the area by the youths as it affects the aged and children. The study recommends measures to limit rapid increase in urbanization, as well as strategies to reduce rural-urban migration and also profound ways of making the rural areas (include) comfortable for rural dwellers.

Paul, Matthias, and Abdellatif, (2021) conducted a study on Impacts of Electricity Outages in Urban Households in Developing Countries: A Case of Accra, Ghana. Many developing countries in Africa face a "double tragedy" when it comes to electrification. Electricity access rates are low, while those who have access to electricity face frequent outages. There are ongoing efforts aimed at increasing access to electricity on the continent. However, the need to improve the reliability of electricity supply receives limited attention. Unreliable electricity impacts users by limiting electricity utilization and the benefits that should accrue from having an electricity connection. Using data from 496 household survey questionnaires, this study examines the impacts of electricity outages in urban households in Accra, Ghana. The study applies correlation and regression analyses to identify which household characteristics are associated with or predict households reporting outage impacts. Outages were found to impact household safety/security, access to food, and access to social services and were found to cause appliance damage as well. Factors that are significantly correlated with reporting certain outage impacts include respondent's annual income and employment status, frequency of electricity outages, and household size. Significant predictors of reporting outage impacts are socioeconomic disadvantage, high exposure to outages, and living in a large family setting. The study's findings underscore the need for interventions to eliminate, or at least minimize, electricity supply interruptions in developing countries if sustainable social and economic development is to be achieved.

Bassey, and Imoh (2021) conducted a study on the Effect of Electricity Supply on the Performance of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises in Nigeria: A Case Study of Calabar South and Calabar Municipality of Cross River State. This research work analyzed the comparative study of the effect of electricity supply on the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Calabar South and Calabar Municipality, using small and medium scale businessmen and women as well as power holding company staff. The objectives of this study to analyze the comparative study of the effect of electricity supply on the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Calabar South and Calabar Municipality. The survey research design was adopted and a twelve (12) item structured questionnaire was used to obtain a sample size of 248 small and medium scale business owners and power holding staff randomly selected from the population. The results of the study revealed that there is a significant effect of electricity supply on the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Calabar South and Calabar Municipality. The results further revealed that insufficient electricity supply significantly affect the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Calabar South and Calabar Municipality. The study concludes that there are enormous difficulties being experienced by businesses in Cross River State and other parts of Nigeria due to inadequate and unreliable electric power supply. Thus, an inadequate and unreliable supply of electricity imposes costs and therefore constrained firms' operational performance as firms suffer high overhead cost due to the deficient electricity supply from the national grid.

Umeora, and Onwuzuligbo (2021) established a study on Significance of Frequency of Power Supply on Residents' Satisfaction in Private Housing Estates in Enugu, Nigeria. The objective of this study was to investigate the frequency of power supply and its relationship with residents' satisfaction with performance of service facilities' in private housing estates in Enugu with a view to providing feedback conditions for improved satisfaction in the private housing estates. The methodology adopted for this research was survey design. The focus was on four private housing estates in Enugu metropolis randomly selected from the research population. After stratification, based on housing type, two hundred and fifty-six occupied housing units were randomly selected. Data was collected from primary sources using questionnaires and observation schedules. Frequency of power supply (which is a service facility variable) and residents' satisfaction with performance of service facilities (a composite variable aggregated from - Satisfaction with power supply source, satisfaction with frequency of power supply, satisfaction with mode of water supply, satisfaction with frequency of water supply) were of interval variables scale; hence, Pearson Product

Moment correlation tool was used to test the significance of the relationship. It was established that there is a significant relationship between frequency of power supply and residents' satisfaction with performance of service facilities in private housing estates in Enugu metropolis with a significant probability value of 0.010. This implies that number of hours electricity is supplied to the housing estates by electricity distribution companies residents affect residents' level of satisfaction within the population of study.

Setu, Narges, Neyrand, and Philipp (2023) conducted a study on Electricity supply quality and use among rural and peri-urban households and small firms in Nigeria. We present a household and enterprise energy survey dataset collected within the framework of the People Sun project in Nigeria in 2021. Across three Nigerian geopolitical zones, a total of 3,599 households and 1,122 small and medium-sized enterprises were surveyed. The sample is designed to be representative of rural and peri-urban grid-electrified regions of each zone. Our surveys collect data on demographic and socioeconomic characteristics, energy access and supply quality, electrical appliance ownership and usage time, cooking solutions, energy related capabilities, and supply preferences. We encourage academic use of the data presented and suggest three avenues of further research: (1) modelling appliance ownership likelihoods, electricity consumption levels and energy service needs in un-electrified regions; (2) identifying supply-side and demand-side solutions to address high usage of diesel generators; (3) exploring broader issues of multi-dimensional energy access, access to decent living standards and climate vulnerability.

Effect of movement rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state

The study conducted by Ishaku, Rafee, Ajayi, and Haruna (2011) sheds light on the pressing issue of water supply in rural Nigerian communities. The central theme of this research revolves around the influence of water supply on the health, economic productivity, and overall quality of life of rural inhabitants in Nigeria. This empirical review paper aims to assess the extent to which water supply has contributed to the development of health, social, and cultural aspects of these communities, given the challenges they face. The study highlights that a substantial majority, over 70%, of households in rural Nigerian communities lack access to improved water supply systems. Instead, they depend on self-water supply sources such as rivers, streams, water ponds, and unprotected wells. This dependence on unimproved water sources exposes the population to waterborne diseases like typhoid fever, cholera, dysentery, and malaria parasites. Notably, these rural areas consist of scattered settlements engaged primarily in farming activities with limited income, making the provision of piped water supply an intricate challenge. The government's efforts to address the water supply issue in rural areas have primarily centered on hand-operated boreholes and wells. However, these sources often yield minimal water during dry seasons and are susceptible to frequent breakdowns, exacerbating water crises and shortages. Consequently, households, especially women and children, must travel longer distances to fetch water for domestic use during these dry spells. The research highlights a crucial need for a shift from the prevailing public monopoly of water supply towards innovative approaches. It suggests rainwater harvesting technology as one such alternative solution. Rainwater harvesting could potentially alleviate the challenges posed by unreliable water sources, reduce disease prevalence, and enhance the overall well-being of rural communities. Ishaku, Rafee, Ajayi, and Haruna's study underscores the critical importance of addressing the water supply dilemma in Nigerian rural communities. The findings emphasize the urgency of adopting innovative solutions like rainwater harvesting to ensure access to safe and reliable water sources, thereby improving the health, socio-economic, and cultural development of these communities.

The research conducted by Dickson et al. (2022) delves into the transformative impact of urbanization and rural-urban migration on public housing delivery in the Enugu metropolis of Nigeria. In the global context, urbanization has gained momentum, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where the shift from rural to urban areas is particularly pronounced. The study primarily examines the consequences of rural-urban migration on housing delivery in Enugu, aiming to develop sustainable measures to address these challenges. The research employs a qualitative research method, involving direct observation and a review of existing literature, to gather primary and secondary data. The findings of the study reveal several effects of urbanization in the Enugu metropolis. These include a substantial housing shortage, rising housing rents, increased land values within the city, leading to the proliferation of squatter settlements on its outskirts, haphazard development, shifts in land use, violations of planning regulations, suboptimal amenities, inadequate infrastructure, and the emergence of slum-like conditions.

Furthermore, the research identifies 14 peri-urban squatter settlements in the study area, housing an estimated population of 62,733 people, equivalent to approximately 5.5% of the unaccounted spill-over population with over 11,082 households in the city. It also underscores that public housing provision in Enugu from 1999 to 2020 disproportionately favored higher-income earners, neglecting a significant portion of the city's population comprising low-income earners. The study concludes by recommending strategic and comprehensive government interventions in the housing sector. It calls for the use of local building materials and advocates for the utilization of housing cooperatives with single-digit interest loans for housing finance to ensure the equitable provision of affordable housing for the city's growing population. Dickson et al.'s research highlights the far-reaching consequences of rural-urban migration and urbanization on public housing delivery in Enugu. The study emphasizes the urgency of addressing housing disparities, infrastructure deficits, and the emergence of informal settlements to achieve more inclusive and sustainable urban development.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu Metropolis. The study made use of small and medium enterprises in Enugu metropolis. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study consisted of three hundred and fifty-one (351) owners and staff. The whole population was used due to small number. Three hundred and forty-six (346) persons returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 99 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.840 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

The effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State

Table 1: Responses to research question one on the effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision	
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X			
1	The increased risk of illness was due to toxic environmental conditions with limited access to medical care	930 186 53.8	220 55 15.9	204 68 19.7	50 25 7.2	12 12 3.5	1416 346 100%	4.09	1.153	Agree	
2	Moving to new place has promoted easy access to health care services	900 180 52.0	220 55 15.9	219 73 21.1	58 26 7.5	12 12 3.5	1409 346 100%	4.07	1.160	Agree	
3	Quick response to health care was as a result of new environment	770 154 44.5	220 55 15.9	297 99 28.6	48 24 6.9	14 14 4.0	1349 346 100%	3.89	1.169	Agree	
4	Mobility improves opportunities for coordinating healthcare	790 158 45.7	328 82 23.7	201 67 19.4	34 17 4.9	22 22 6.4	1375 346 100%	3.97	1.193	Agree	
5	The extent of good healthcare was as a result of transit decisions and actions	920 184 53.2	976 94 27.2	102 34 9.8	34 17 4.9	17 17 4.9	2049 346 100%	5.92	1.112	Agree	
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.836	1.3214		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 241 respondents out of 346 representing 69.7percent agreed that the increased risk of illness was due to toxic environmental conditions with limited access to medical care with mean score 4.09 and a standard deviation of 1.153. Moving to new place has promoted easy access to health care services 235 respondents representing 67.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.07and a standard deviation of 1.160. Quick response to health care was as a result of new environment 209 respondents representing 60.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.89and standard deviation of 1.169. Mobility improves opportunities for coordinating healthcare 240 respondents representing 69.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.97and 1.193. The extent of good healthcare was as a result of transit decisions and actions 278 respondents representing 80.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 5.92and a standard deviation of 1.112.

The effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State
Table 2: Responses to research question Two on the effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The movement to new location enabled access for use of electricity	780 156 45.1	460 115 33.2	90 30 8.7	76 38 11.0	7 7 2.0	1413 346 100.0	2.88	1.075	Agree
2	Being among electrified communities there is operating of electrical appliances	810 162 47.1	500 125 36.1	93 31 9.0	16 8 2.3	19 19 5.5	1438 346 100%	4.15	1.059	Agree
3	The shift to city has improved living standard by stimulating the business enterprise	970 194 56.1	420 105 30.3	90 30 8.7	10 5 1.4	12 12 3.5	1502 346 100%	4.34	.951	Agree
4	Electricity aids to cook and store food as move to another locations	895 179 51.7	512 128 37.0	51 17 4.9	28 14 4.0	8 8 2.3	1494 346 100%	4.31	.915	Agree
5	Harnessing electricity in the new location paved the way to lots of job opportunity	670 134 38.7	612 153 44.2	51 17 4.9	68 34 9.8	8 8 2.3	1409 346 100.0	4.07	1.018	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.836	1.3214	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 271 respondents out of 346 representing 78.3 percent agreed that the movement to new location enabled access for use of electricity with mean score 2.88 and a standard deviation of 1.075. Being among electrified communities there is operating of electrical appliances 287 respondents representing 83.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.15and a standard deviation of 1.059. The shift to city has improved living standard by stimulating the business enterprise 299 respondents representing 86.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.34 and standard deviation of .951. Electricity aids to cook and store food as move to another locations 307 respondents representing 88.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.31and .915. Harnessing electricity in the new location paved the way to lots of job opportunity 287 respondents representing 82.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.07and a standard deviation of 1.018.

Table 3: Responses to research question three on the effect of movement from rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne ater in urban centres in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Leaving the rural-urban area to urban we have improved water quality	755 151 43.6	460 115 33.2	90 30 8.7	60 30 11.3	11 11 3.2	1376 346 100%	4.0289	1.12380	Agree
2	The arrival to the city saved cost related to diseases due to quality drinking water	815 163 47.1	500 125 36.1	93 31 9.0	24 12 3.5	15 15 4.3	1447 346 100%	4.1821	1.0293 2	Agree
3	The Movement from rural-urban saved travel and waiting time for water collected	940 188 54.2	420 105 30.3	90 30 8.7	24 12 3.5	11 11 3.2	1485 346 100%	4.2919	.98616	Agree
4	Reliable access to clean water in the urban area increased overall hygiene behaviours	890 178 51.4	512 128 37.0	51 17 4.9	30 15 4.3	8 8 2.3	1491 346 100%	4.3092	.92299	Agree
5	Clean water increases the availability of Wash resources in the urban area	650 130 37.6	612 153 44.2	51 17 4.9	64 32 9.2	14 14 4.0	1391 346 100%	4.0202	1.0779 2	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.16646	1.02803 8	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3, 266 respondents out of 346 representing 76.8 percent agreed that leaving the rural-urban area to urban we have improved water quality with mean score 4.0289 and a standard deviation of 1.12380. The arrival to the city saved cost related to diseases due to quality drinking water 288 respondents representing 83.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.1821 and a standard deviation of 1.02932. The Movement from rural-urban saved travel and waiting time for water collected 293 respondents representing 84.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.2919 and standard deviation of .98616. Reliable access to clean water in the urban area increased overall hygiene behaviours 306 respondents representing 88.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.3092 and .92299. Clean water increases the availability of Wash resources in the urban area 283 respondents representing 81.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.0202 and a standard deviation of 1.07792.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Transit to a new environment has effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State

Table 4: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		The increased risk of illness was due to toxic environmental conditions with limited access to medical care	Moving to new place has promoted easy access to health care services	Quick response to health care was as a result of new environment	Mobility improves opportunities for coordinating healthcare	The extent of good healthcare was as a result of transit decisions and actions
N		346	346	346	346	346
Uniform Parameter $s^{a,b}$	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.538	.520	.445	.457	.553
	Positive	.035	.035	.040	.064	.049
	Negative	-.538	-.520	-.445	-.457	-.553
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		9.999	9.677	8.279	8.494	10.295
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $8.279 < 10.293$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that transit to a new environment had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $8.279 < 10.293$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that transit to a new environment had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two: Acclimation to a new location has effect on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State

Table 5: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		The movement to new location enabled access for use of electricity	Being among electrified communities there is operating of electrical appliances	The shift to city has improved living standard by stimulating the business enterprise	Electricity aids to cook and store food as move to another locations	Harnessing electricity in the new location paved the way to lots of job opportunity
N		346	346	346	346	346
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.533	.582	.614	.637	.579
	Positive	.020	.055	.035	.023	.023
	Negative	-.533	-.582	-.614	-.637	-.579
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		9.919	10.833	11.424	11.854	10.779
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $9.919 < 10.833$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Acclimation to a new location had significant positive effect on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $9.919 < 10.833$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Acclimation to a new location had significant positive effect on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Three: Movement from rural-urban has effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Leaving the rural-urban area to urban we have improved water quality	The arrival to the city saved cost related to diseases due to quality drinking water	The Movement from rural-urban saved travel and waiting time for water collected	Reliable access to clean water in the urban area increased overall hygiene behaviours	Clean water increases the availability of Wash resources in the urban area
N		346	346	346	346	346
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Maximum	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.519	.582	.597	.634	.568
	Positive	.032	.043	.032	.023	.040
	Negative	-.519	-.582	-.597	-.634	-.568
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		9.650	10.833	11.102	11.800	10.564
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $9.650 < 11.102$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Movement from rural-urban had significance positive effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $9.650 < 11.102$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Movement from rural-urban had significance positive effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state.**

Discussion of Findings

The effect of transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State

From the result of hypothesis one, comparing the calculated Z- value of $8.279 < 10.293$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that transit to a new environment had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Alhaji, and Lawal (2017), conducted a study on Urbanization, Cities, and Health: The Challenges to Nigeria – A Review. It was revealed that Urban health development requires intersect oral approach with political will and urban renewal program to make our urban societies sustainable that promote healthy living. Nnebue, Echendu, and Sidney-nnebue, (2014), conducted a study on Urbanization and health - an overview. The health of urban populations has changed as cities have evolved as a result of such factors as features of the social environment, the physical environment, and provision of and access to health and social services.

The effect of acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State

From the result of hypothesis two, comparing the calculated Z- value of $9.919 < 10.833$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that Acclimation to a new location had significant positive effect on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Umeora, and Onwuzuligbo, (2021), established a study on Significance of Frequency of Power Supply on Residents' Satisfaction in Private Housing Estates in Enugu, Nigeria. It was established that there is a significant relationship between frequency of power supply and residents' satisfaction with performance of service facilities' in private housing estates in Enugu metropolis with a significant probability value of 0.010. Setu, Bassey, and Imoh (2021), conducted a study on the Effect of Electricity Supply on the Performance of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises in Nigeria: A Case Study of Calabar South and Calabar Municipality of Cross River State. The results of the study revealed that there is a significant effect of electricity supply on the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Calabar South and Calabar Municipality.

The effect of Movement from rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state

From the result of hypothesis three, the calculated Z- value of $9.650 < 11.102$ against the critical Z- value of .000 implies states that **Movement from rural-urban had significance positive effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state**. In the support of the result in the literature review Dickson, Francis, Christopher, Rosemary, Okeke & Nwosu, (2022) A Study of the Impact of Rural-Urban Migration and Urbanization on Public Housing Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Nigeria. Globally, urbanization is now like a tidal wave sweeping the entire world and its impact is felt more in developing countries like Nigeria, where urban growth is marked by a dramatic shift with emphasis from rural to urban centers. Rural-urban migration which is one of the effects of urbanization has had grievous implications for urban housing delivery in Nigerian cities. The research results highlight some of the effects of Urbanization in the study area to include; gross housing shortage, increase housing rent and high land value in the city resulting to the emergence and expansion of many squatter settlements at the periphery of the city, incidence of haphazard situation of developments, change in land uses, violation of planning guidelines, suboptimal amenities and inadequate infrastructure as well as slum conditions. The study also identified 14 peri-urban squatter settlements with an estimated total population of 62,733 people; an indication of about 5.5% unaccounted spill over population with over 11,082 households in the city.

Summary of Findings

1. Transit to a new environment had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare in urban Centres in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 346), 8.279 < 10.293, P. < .05$.
2. Acclimation to a new location had significant positive effect on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 346), 9.919 < 10.833, P. < .05$.
3. Movement from rural-urban had significance positive effect on the provision of pipe borne water in urban centres in Enugu state, $Z(95, n = 346), 9.650 < 11.102, P. < .05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that transit to a new environment, Acclimation to a new location and Movement from rural-urban had significant positive effect on the provision of healthcare, electricity supply and provision of pipe borne water in Urban Centres in Enugu State. migration is a phenomenon of great complexity. The reasons people migrate are varied and constantly changing. Moreover, the individuals who migrate are not easy to classify due to the fact that they come under different circumstances, from different environments and with different individual characteristics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendation were proffered

- i. There is need for rural development to reduce why people migrate in search of income differences in the urban centres.
- ii. For effective skills acquisition there is need to Migrate boosts the working-age population and contribute to human capital— development for the country technological progress.
- iii. The government should be away of the people plight about water and connect the masses both those in rural urban to a reliable and secure rural piped water supply, such as: Improved water quality that is not exposed to contaminants en-route or through surface runoff. Better quality water for bathing and washing than many dams.

Contribution to Knowledge

Some studies done were carried outside effect of migration on the provision of social amenities in Urban Centres in Enugu State and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the transit to a new environment on the provision of healthcare; acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply and Movement from rural-urban on the provision of pipe borne water in Urban Centres in Enugu State. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, analyzed using table and lines, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study filled the research gap by evaluating the acclimation to a new location on the provision of electricity supply in Urban Centres in Enugu State.

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